

VALKYRIES

D2.6 Harmonization and Standardization Reports M6

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Ignacio Hernandez Palencia	Ignacio.hernandez@novotec.es	NOVOTEC

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Annabel Sivila Castellana Manuel Ocaña	INDRA	Revision
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	Revision/Edit

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, out comes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.6 *Harmonization and Standardization Reports* presents the status of the project in terms of standardisation and harmonisation.

The harmonization and standardization process is a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous competence/knowledge shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, specific procedures (and their differences between regions/countries), evaluation and information exchange.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Harmonization and Standardization Reports

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3. Introduction

This deliverable is the first harmonization and standardization report. There will be a report every 6 months until the end of the project as it is defining in the programme.

The last deliverable D2.4, about the standardization roadmap, provides an effective base for developing and controlling the harmonization process. It is necessary to keep it in mind for understanding the steps required on this deliverable.

The requirements and definition of the use cases have been agreed recently and the scope of the project has been defined in depth.

Tasks on the WP4, WP5 and WP6 started just two months ago. So that no major progress has been made in this area.

4. Objectives

The main objective of the deliverable is to reprove the progress of standardization and harmonization of Valkyries.

The secondary objectives of this report are:

- Collect the standardization actions that the partners are carrying out.
- Identify the lack of progress in some parts.
- Check that the project is in line with the roadmap.

5. Current status of the pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization.

The harmonization and standardization of the project is in its first steps.

As a reminder of deliverable D2.4 about the standardization roadmap. Novotec defined 3 phases for the harmonization process. In this first harmonisation report we are understandably in the first harmonization phase.

In this first phase of the harmonization, we are in the process of collecting information and mapping standards. Some use cases and requirements have been defined recently and therefore not all documents that could affect the project were known; this had to be considered in order to provide time to collect the information.

As a reminder of deliverable D2.4 about the standardisation roadmap. Novotec defined 3 phases for the harmonisation process. Obviously in this first harmonisation report we are in the first harmonization phase.

The state of standardization and harmonization is in the first phase: “Existing state-of-the-art”

In the following *Figure 1* we can see the harmonization process of the project and we can identify the current phase of the project, as well as its future intended steps:

Figure 1 - Valkyries harmonisation process

The collection of this legislation and gap that apply to the use cases and to the project are the basis for providing a common reference point for the discussion about operational processes in cross-border and cross-sectoral emergencies.

The harmonization processes of some areas are directly linked to one or more tasks. Almost all of these tasks fall under WP3, WP4 or WP5. As these tasks started only two months ago, some standardization processes are still in the creation part.

To achieve this main objective, VALKYRIES has defined nine specific and measurable objectives described in the following subsections.

5.1. Legal standard identification

5.1.1. Formant description

This format collects information that affects the whole sector or the involved countries.

All the standards related to the project must be collected and all the standards that directly affect VALYRIES in the Use Cases (UC) must be collected too.

The information is sorted for every UC and a common part with documents that are applicable for every UCs. This format could be filled out by all partners, although each partner will provide more information on their native country. Nevertheless, any partner could add the documents and information that may affect the project.

5.1.2. Current status M6

A large number of legal standards, procedures and laws have been collected in this first period. In total around 60 documents have been identified as relevant to the project. These identified documents will be very important in future stages and will help to provide a common point of discussion.

More procedures have been detected for UC1 than for the other use cases.

The added documents have not been double-checked. They may contain information that is not totally relevant to the project or may be incomplete. See Annex A: Legal standard Identification.

5.2. Pre-identification of gaps

5.2.1. Formant description

This format collects pre-identified gaps and commonalities detected by partners. Some data, like the aforementioned gaps and commonalities, can be detected before the meetings with the partners. This is because there is experience, literature and previous projects about these gaps and commonalities.

Smaller-scale drills could be organised in different countries to detect gaps before the use cases.

There are two types of collecting this data:

- Personal experience: The partners' experience in emergencies and their cross-border and cross-sectoral knowledge allows them to identify gaps based on their own personal experience.
- Literature and previous projects: There are previous literature and projects that have already identified gaps. This studied and verified information can be very helpful. In addition, these previous works can support our results.

5.2.2. Current status M6

Some gaps have been identified during this first period. It is true that more gaps could be identified and recorded. This may be related to the start two months ago of the WP3, WP4 and WP5. When individual harmonizations begin, there will be more gaps in the literature on which to base for the next steps.

Without any doubt, the gaps provided are very valuable and will be the subject of discussion in future stages of harmonization.

The added documents have not yet been double-checked. They may contain information that is not totally relevant to the project or may be incomplete. See Annex B: Pre-identification gaps.

5.3. Matrix tool

5.3.1. Formant description

This format is designed to make a comparison between the countries of the Use Cases in different areas will be made. Therefore, there will be a matrix tool for each Use Case (UC).

This collection of information is essential since it is the fundamental pillar of the analysis of the partners' methodology in both parts of the border.

To make this comparison, the matrix tool will be used. For this reason, recorded and classified data will be compared. There are different types of matching depending on the type of data. The comparison will be different and the complexity of the data should be taken into account. It is not the same situation to compare. As in other formats, partners must provide the necessary information for the comparison. Nevertheless, each partner will bring more information from their native country.

5.3.2. Current status M6

The use of this format has only just begun, it only started in UC1. This format is included in the next stage of the harmonization, but not all use cases advance to the same level.

UC1 is more advanced than the rest. More partners and more collaboration make this use case more advanced also in terms of harmonization.

This use case is one step ahead and has started to include information and graphing in the matrix tool. The Spanish part is also more advanced than the Portuguese part for the same reasons.

The harmonization lines are related to the tasks of the project. This relationship can be seen in the first lines of the format pages.

The added documents have not been double-checked. They may contain information that is not totally relevant to the project or may be incomplete. See Annex C: Matrix UC1

5.4. Standardization roadmap

Figure 2 - European pre-standardization map and joint roadmap

5.5. Road map justification

VALKYRIES is on track with the roadmap.

VALKYRIES project has a strong complexity as it is being developed by companies and researchers from different countries, with different expertise and professional skills, which may affect the project development and timeline.

Nevertheless, the project is succeeding to follow the roadmap.

6. Next steps

Following the harmonisation procedure, the next steps will be to complete the collection of procedures by filling the formant "Legal standard identification" and also filling the formant "Pre-identification of gaps".

At a later stage begin to compare procedures in different countries and sectors. This will take place in the coming months as the project stages progress.

7. Annex A – Legal Standard identification

VALKYRIES

Legal Standard Identification

Reference Number: D2.5.2

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Main Contributor: NOVOTEC

**Other Contributors: SERMAS, AREU, TASSICA,
HESE, ISEMI, BDI, KEMEA, HRT**

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Ignacio Hernández	ignacio.hernandez@novotec.es	NOVOTEC

Contributors

Name	Contact	Entity

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Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction/Scope	Publication date/In force	Country/Region	Link
T7.5 -UC1: Spain-Portugal Leader: Servicio de urgencias y emergencias de la comunidad de Madrid SUMMA112 (SMS)						
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	(Madrid) Order 1102.2003. Training Sanitary Vehicles - SPANISH	Minimum training standards for the sanitary professionals and drivers for sanitary vehicles	12/11/2003	Community of madrid	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	(Madrid) Order 22.2014_Sanitary professional qualification - SPANISH	Professional qualification for sanitary professional and drivers for sanitary vehicles	13/03/2014	Community of madrid	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	RD.22.14. Sanitary equipment for sanitary vehicles - SPANISH	Sanitary vehicles Professional staffing (Minimum) on vehicles	25/01/2014	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	RD. 836.2012. technical equipment for sanitary vehicles - SPANISH	Technical characteristics for sanitary vehicles description of professional staffing on vehicles	25/05/2012	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	Order PCI.488.2019_Civil protection. National strategy (Spain-Portugal) - SPANISH	Holistic approach for emergencies and civil protection	30/04/2019	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI (navid.behzadi@salud.madrid.org)	Protocol The Kingdom of Spain and Republic of Portugal on cooperation in emergency situations - SPANISH	It establishes a mutual collaboration between the kingdom of Spain and the republic of Portugal	10/09/2019	Spain/Portugal	LINK
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	Law 2.1985, civil protection	General law about civil protection	21/01/1985	Spain	LINK
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	Royal Decree 513/2017, approves the Regulation of fire protection installations.	Fire protection installations. Just in case that some infrastructure are involved in the Use Case	12/07/2017	Spain	LINK
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	BASIC HANDBOOK OF THE FOREST FIREFIGHTER (EXTREMADURA)	BASIC HANDBOOK OF THE FOREST FIREFIGHTER. SPAIN'S SIDE OF UC1. Operational protocol.		Spain/Extremadura	LINK

AREU	Andrea Comelli (a.comelli@areu.lombardia.it) Monica Ghinaglia (m.ghinaglia@areu.lombardia.it)	• DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 2 gennaio 2018, n. 224 - Codice della protezione civile. (18G00011) – (GU n.17 del 22-1-2018)	Referring to the emergency plan for hydrogeological events, including forest fires, AREU cooperates, not only for the drafting of the plan, but also sending the most appropriate resources (human and technical) in case of medical aid is needed.		Italy	LINK
AREU	Andrea Comelli (a.comelli@areu.lombardia.it) Monica Ghinaglia (m.ghinaglia@areu.lombardia.it)	• Aggiornamento della direttiva regionale per la gestione organizzativa e funzionale del sistema di allertamento per i rischi naturali ai fini di protezione civile (d.p.c.m. 27/02/2004)	Referring to the emergency plan for hydrogeological events, including forest fires, AREU cooperates, not only for the drafting of the plan, but also sending the most appropriate resources (human and technical) in case of medical aid is needed.		Italy	LINK
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Law 10/2019, of April 11, on Civil Protection and Emergency Management of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura	Order actions in emergencies and regulate, within the framework of state and European legislation, the powers of the autonomous community in matters of civil protection	In force 17/20/2019, published DOE 17/04/2019	Spain/Extremadura	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Territorial Plan of Civil Protection of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (PLATERCAEX)	The purpose of the plan is to prevent the loss of human life and property in different emergency situations. It contains the basic concepts to develop the operational structure of civil protection. Its scope is the territory of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura in terms of geographical scope and the general risks that may affect the autonomous community except for special risks that have their own planning.	DECREE 187/2019, of October 15. published in DOE No. 247 of December 26, 2019.	Spain/Extremadura	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Forest fire fighting plan of the autonomous community of extremadura (INFOEX)	It establishes the measures for the detection and extinction of forest fires and the resolution of the situations that arise from them. Its scope is alla the mountains, understanding as such the lands defined in article 5 of the mountain law 10/2006.	Decree 52/2010, of March 5	Spain/Extremadura	

TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Law 17/2015, of July 9, on the National Civil Protection System	Establish the national civil protection system as an essential instrument to ensure the coordination, cohesion and effectiveness of public civil protection policies, and regulate the powers of the general administration of the state in the matter	In force on 10 January, 2016, published in BOE No. 164 of July 10, 2015	Spain	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	State Plan of Civil Protection for Emergency Situations	The objective of the state plan is to establish the organization and action procedures to ensure an effective response by all public administrations in emergency cases due to forest fires in which the national interest is present, as well as, in other cases, to provide the necessary support to the plans of the autonomous communities when they require it. The scope of action covers the entire national territory.	November 8, BOE November 7	Spain	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Protocol between the Kingdom of Spain and the Republic of Portugal on Technical Cooperation and Mutual Assistance in Civil Protection matters	The protocol covers scientific and technical cooperation between the two countries that, on a reciprocal basis, may request help from the other party in cases of emergency or catastrophe or in anticipation of these. The executing services will be the National Civil Protection Service of Portugal and the General Directorate of Civil Protection and Emergency of Spain.	In force on July 2, 1993, published in BOE No. 175 of July 23, 1993	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Treaty between the Kingdom of Spain and the Portuguese Republic on cross-border cooperation	Its purpose is to promote and legally regulate cross-border cooperation between Portuguese authorities and Spanish territorial entities within the scope of their respective competences. the treaty specifies the regions and municipalities of application.	In force on January 30, 2004, BOE 219 of September 12, 2003	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto (carmen.martin@tassica.com)	Additional protocol on mutual aid in case of forest fires	Its purpose is to establish the conditions and procedures for the provision of assistance or relief and the requirements for the provision of resources in the event of an emergency due to forest fires in border areas between Spain and Portugal. Aplicable to border areas that, both of the Porgueses and Spanish side, they are made up of the bordering municipalities	BOE 34/02/7, 2018	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	

HESE	Miguel Gaspar (mcfgaspar@hevora.m in-saude.pt)	National Forest Fire Defense Plan (PNDFCI)	Increasing the territory's resilience to forest fires; Reducing the incidence of wildfires; Improving the effectiveness of attack and management of wildfires; Recovering and rehabilitating ecosystems; Adaptation of a functional and efficient organic structure	April 2006	Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar (mcfgaspar@hevora.m in-saude.pt)	Civil Protection National Plan of Emergency	National plan that seeks to set the guidelines of responses in case of natural disasters such as forest fires, earthquakes, flooding, rupture of dams, heatwaves, etc.	July 18 2008	Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar (mcfgaspar@hevora.m in-saude.pt)	Évora Municipal Emergency Plan	Establishing criteria and technical standards for the preparation and operationalization of civil protection emergency plans	July 2012	Évora, Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar (mcfgaspar@hevora.m in-saude.pt)	National Strategy of Adaptation to Climate Change	Aims to improve the level of knowledge on climate change and promote the integration of adaptation to climate change in sectoral policies and territorial planning instruments. The ENAAC also aims to help central, regional and local administration and policy makers to find the means and tools to implement adaptation solutions based on scientific and technical knowledge and best practices.	April 2010	Portugal	
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Spain	LINK

T7.6 -UC2: Slovakia-Austria. Leader ISEMI

ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	Civil Protection Act	The purpose of this Act is to regulate the conditions for effective protection of life, health and property from the consequences of emergencies, as well as to establish the roles and responsibilities of state administration bodies, self-governing regions, municipalities and rights and obligations of natural persons and legal entities in ensuring civil protection.	05/2021	Slovakia	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC)	DRPC - main objective is to ensure that surface waters and groundwater within the Danube River Basin are managed and used sustainably and equitably. This involves: (a) the conservation, improvement and rational use of surface water and groundwater, (b) preventive measures to control hazards originating from accidents involving floods, ice or hazardous substances, (c) measures to reduce the pollution loads entering the Black Sea from sources in the Danube River Basin.	10/1998	14 Danube countries	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	DANUBE DECLARATION	The declaration addresses the border-crossing problems along the Danube corridor, regarding environmental protection and the risk of floods, and is also in line with the EU Water Framework Directive.	9.2.2016	14 Danube countries	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	EU Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC	The Water Framework Directive stipulates that groundwater must achieve good quantitative status and good chemical status. Chemical quality refers to environmental quality standards for river basin specific pollutants. These standards specify maximum concentrations for specific water pollutants.	22.12.2000	Member States	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	DIRECTIVE 2004/35/CE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL	The purpose of this Directive is to establish a framework of environmental liability to prevent and remedy environmental damage.	21.4.2004	Member States	LINK

ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio (korpesio@isemi.sk)	COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 1999/31/EC	The aim of this Directive is, by way of stringent operational and technical requirements on the waste and landfills, to provide for measures, procedures and guidance to prevent or reduce as far as possible negative effects on the environment, in particular the pollution of surface water, groundwater, soil and air, and on the global environment, including the greenhouse effect, as well as any resulting risk to human health, from landfilling of waste, during the whole life-cycle of the landfill.	26.4.1999	Member States	LINK
AREU	Andrea Comelli (a.comelli@areu.lombardia.it) Monica Ghinaglia (m.ghinaglia@areu.lombardia.it)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DD.MM 25/2/86 e 21/3/86• Procedura attivazione della Scorta Nazionale Antidoti (SNA) Marzo 2015• D.Lgs. n. 334 del 17 agosto 1999 -) D.G.R. n. 15496 del 5 dicembre 2003• Direttiva Regionale Grandi Rischi: linee guida per la gestione delle emergenze chimico industriali (ai sensi della L.R. n. 1/2000, art. 3, comma 131)• D.d.g n. 10872 Nov. 2014 Protocollo operativo in materia di Bioterrorismo• Presidenza Consiglio dei Ministri 2004 Piano Sanitario di Emergenza in caso di attacco terroristico con aggressivi chimici	Based on the documents listed above, AREU has implemented procedures and operating indications in order to manage an event with high risk of chemical or bacteriological contamination considering the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Precautions to be taken.• Cooperation with the subjects assigned to the rescue phase.• Procedures to be adopted for an intervention that adequately protects the health personnel.• Identification of other priorities to be adopted for an accomplished and correct intervention to protect the intoxicated / contaminated.		Italy	

NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Slovakia	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Austria	LINK

T7.7 -UC3: Bulgaria-Greece						
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev (y.yanakiev@di.mod.bg)	DISASTER PROTECTION ACT of the Republic of Bulgaria	This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters. Art. 4. The main principles of disaster protection shall be:	Prom. SG. 102/19 Dec 2006, last amend. SG. 80/14 Oct 2011	Republic of Bulgaria	
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev (y.yanakiev@di.mod.bg)	MINISTRY OF THE INTERIOR ACT Prom. SG. 53/27 Jun 2014	Section V. Provision of Fire Safety and Protection in Fires, Disasters and Emergencies Section V "a". Art. 17. (1) The activities of providing fire safety and protection in fires, disasters and emergencies shall be carried out by the authorities of fire safety and protection of the population under the conditions and procedure of this act Section VI. Enabling access of citizens to the emergency services through the National Emergency Calls System with SEN 112 (new - SG 14/15)	41796	Republic of Bulgaria	

<p>BDI (Leader)</p>	<p>Yantsislav Yanakiev (y.yanakiev@di.mod.bg)</p>	<p>ACT ON THE NATIONAL EMERGENCY SYSTEM WITH A SINGLE EUROPEAN CALL NUMBER 112, Prom. SG. 102/28 Nov 2008</p>	<p>This Act shall regulate the structure and functions of the National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112 The National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112, the responsibilities for its setting up, maintenance and development, as well as the rights and the obligations of the citizens using the single European emergency call number 112.</p>	<p>39780</p>	<p>Republic of Bulgaria</p>	
<p>BDI (Leader)</p>	<p>Yantsislav Yanakiev (y.yanakiev@di.mod.bg)</p>	<p>Act on the Management and Functioning of the System of National Security Protection</p>	<p>This act defines the national security protection system, the tasks and responsibilities of the institutions and services included in this system, the coordination between them, and the control over their operation</p>	<p>Promulgated, SG No. 61/11.08.2015, effective 1.11.2015</p>	<p>Republic of Bulgaria</p>	
<p>AREU</p>	<p>Andrea Comelli (a.comelli@areu.lombardia.it) Monica Ghinaglia (m.ghinaglia@areu.lombardia.it)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreto del 13 Febbraio 2001 Criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri del 28 Giugno 2011 • Indirizzi operativi per l'attivazione e la gestione dei moduli sanitari in caso di catastrofe - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri - Repertorio 1993 del 24 Giugno 2016 	<p>The documents mentioned, define the response methods of receivers, of human resources, logistical and structural resources and special teams in case of regional, extra-regional, national accident of the "seismic event" type.</p> <p>The "USAR" (urban search and rescue) teams work in cooperation with the National Fire Brigade, according to organizational, managerial and operational standards aimed to encouraging the development of operational units for the search and rescue of those missing under rubble, constituted by personnel in possession of high qualifications, in line with the "good practices" defined in the international field by the guidelines of the International Search And Rescue Advisory Group (INSAGAR, latest update in 2020).</p> <p>Urban search and rescue is a type of technical rescue operation that involves the location, extrication, and initial medical stabilization of victims trapped in an urban area, namely structural collapse due to natural disasters, war, terrorism or accidents, mines and collapsed trenches.</p>		<p>Italy</p>	

KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Xenokratis (Ministerial Decision 1299/2003–Government Gazette 423 B/10-04-2003)	National General Plan for Civil Protection, aiming at effective response to catastrophic phenomena for the protection of life, health and property of citizens, as well as the protection of the natural environment	10.04.2003	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	National Law 4662/20 (OGG27 A 4662/07.02.2020)	National Crisis Management and Risk Management Mechanism, Restructuring of the National Secretariat for Civil Protection, upgrading a system of voluntary policy protection, reorganization of the Fire and other provisions.	07.02.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	National Special Human Loss Man	This plan defines a system for the proper organization and coordination of stakeholders and services, to effectively manage incidents with numerous deaths as a result of physical, technological (including biological, chemical, radiological and nuclear events) and other disasters as well as criminal and terrorist acts.	18.12.2019	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Action Plan Egkelados	General Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes	30.01.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Template Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes for the municipalities of the Hellenic territory	A template for the setting up of emergency response plan for Municipalities of the Hellenic Territory	19.06.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Action Plan “Dardanos”	General Action Plan for emergency response and short-term management of floods impacts	6.12.2019	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Joint Ministerial Decision 31822/1542/E103 (OGG B 1108/21.07.2010)	Incorporation of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC in the Greek National Law	21.07.2010	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Flood Risk Management Plan for the Water District of Central Macedonia	Implementation of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC in the Water District close to the area of interest of Demonstrator #3	05.07.2018	Greece	LINK

KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	PD128 (OGG9717 A 228/07.12.2016)	Incorporation of the ATEX 214 “equipment” Directive 2014/34/EU–Equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres in the Greek National Law	07.12.2016	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	PD42 (OGG493 A 44/21.02.2003)	Incorporation of ATEX 137 “workplace” Directive 1999/92/EC– Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers potentially at risk from explosive atmospheres in the Greek National Law	21.02.2003	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	Chrysoula Papathanasiou (c.papathanasiou@kemea-research.gr)	Action Plan Herakleitos	General Action Plan for emergency response due to large scale technological accidents (General SATAME)	06.02.2020	Greece	LINK
HRT	Iosif Vourvachis (i.vourvachis@hrt.org.gr) Dimitris Iliadis (d.iliadis@hrt.org.gr)	INSARAG GUIDELINES 2020	The INSARAG Guidelines provides a methodology to guide countries affected by a sudden-onset disaster causing large-scale structural collapse, as well as international USAR Teams responding in the affected country	2020	UN	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Bulgaria	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Greece	LINK

T7.8 -UC4: Norway-Netherlands-Denmark

AREU	Andrea Comelli (a.comelli@areu.lombardia.it) Monica Ghinaglia (m.ghinaglia@areu.lombardia.it)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreto Ministero dell'Interno 13 Febbraio 2001 "Adozione dei criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi Decreto del 13 Febbraio 2001 Criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri del 28 Giugno 2011 	<p>Actually, a maritime disaster scenario is unlikely in Lombardy, but it is conceivable in contests as lakes, rivers or streams.</p> <p>We do not have specific reference documentation but we are investigating the issue with our colleagues of Emergency call dispatch points in charge of Lakes Area.</p>		Italy	
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) - Adoption: 1973 (Convention), 1978 (1978 Protocol), 1997 (Protocol - Annex VI); Entry into force: 2 October 1983 (Annexes I and II).	The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) is the main international convention covering prevention of pollution of the marine environment by ships from operational or accidental causes.	Adoption: 1973 (Convention), 1978 (1978 Protocol)	International	
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceeded overview Could be a source of more information.	2021	Denmark	LINK

Common to all use cases						
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	M/487 EN. PROGRAMMING MANDATE ADDRESSED TO CEN, CENELEC AND ETSI TO ESTABLISH SECURITY STANDARDS	This Mandate concerns the development of a work programme for the definition of European Standards and other standardisation deliverables in the area of SECURITY. The programme will take note of all aspects linked to the different specific products, systems, procedures and protocols that should be covered by standards to assist the EU to ensure that security is better and consistently addressed in different security landscapes. This Mandate has an exclusively civil application focus.	17/02/2011	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	DECISION No 1313/2013/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL	1.This Decision shall apply to cooperation in the field of civil protection. (a)prevention and preparedness actions inside the Union. (b) actions to assist with the response to immediate adverse consequences of a disaster inside or outside the Union. 2. Shall take into account the special needs (e.g. isolated, islands, overseas countries) in terms of prevention of.	13/12/2013	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	COUNCIL DECISION of 23 October 2001 establishing a Community mechanism to facilitate reinforced cooperation in civil protection assistance interventions	In the event of a major emergency within the Community, or imminent threat thereof, which causes, or is capable of causing, transboundary effects or which may result in a call for assistance from one or more Member States, there is a need for relevant notification to be made as appropriate through an established reliable common emergency communication and information system.	15/11/2001	Member States	LINK

NOVOTEC	Alicia Cabeza (alicia.cabeza@novotec.es)	COUNCIL DECISION of 8 November 2007 establishing a Community Civil Protection Mechanism (recast) (Text with EEA relevance) (2007/779/EC, Euratom)	The Mechanism should facilitate the civil protection response to all types of major emergencies occurring inside or outside the Community, including natural and man-made disasters, acts of terrorism and technological, radiological and environmental accidents, including accidental marine pollution. Civil protection assistance may be required in all of these emergencies to complement the response capabilities of the affected country.	11/12/2007	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceeds overview. Could be a source of more information.	2021	Member States	LINK

8. Annex B – Pre-identification of gaps

VALKYRIES

Pre-identification of gaps

Reference Number: 2.5.1

Ed/Rev: A/1

Main Contributor: NOVOTEC
Other Contributors: IND, TAS, SSA

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Ignacio Hernández	ignacio.hernandez@novotec.es	NOVOTEC

Contributors

Name	Contact	Entity
		TAS
		SSA
		IND

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A/1	30/03/2021	All	Information filled in M6

WP2- Responsible innovation, certification and exploitation			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Terminology and Semantic	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency: Issue/gap:	
	Literature "Different language"	Doc name: South Eastern Europe Disaster Risk Mitigation and Adaptation Initiative Year: 2008 Link: https://www.unisdr.org/files/1741_SouthEasternEuropeDRMitigation.pdf	NOVOTEC
		Justification: Most of the countries in the South Eastern Europe have gone through major political, social, economic and administrative changes, and this is reflected in the institutional aspects of disaster risk management. Presently, most of these countries are moving with rejuvenated energy towards development, and are in modes conducive to integrating disaster management into the development process. In some countries, there is a shift from military to civil administration in the disaster management structures.	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency: Issue/gap: Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name: Year: Link: Justification:	

WP3- Responsible innovation, certification and exploitation			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Operational procedures	Professional experience "identification of the first triage"	<p>Doc name: Lack of homogeneity in the labeling of victims after first triage</p> <p>Justification: Different triage systems are used for different emergency services in order to prioritize casualties in a disaster situation, some emergency teams have their own system which allows them to identify the characteristics and severity of the victim with, for example, a certain color (red, yellow, green or black). Not all emergency services use the same system to identify the severity of the patient with the same colors; in a first triage, the identification system can be a bracelet, tape, make a sign or letter on the skin, or a triage card. This can make confusion between different services, produce important mistakes, and be a waste of time trying to understand the system.</p>	TASSICA
	Literature "Different institutional management"	<p>Doc name: South Eastern Europe Disaster Risk Mitigation and Adaptation Initiative</p> <p>Year: 2008</p> <p>Link: https://www.unisdr.org/files/1741_SouthEasternEuropeDRMitigation.pdf</p> <p>Justification: Most of the countries in the South Eastern Europe have gone through major political, social, economic and administrative changes, and this is reflected in the institutional aspects of disaster risk management. Presently, most of these countries are moving with rejuvenated energy towards development, and are in modes conducive to integrating disaster management into the development process. In some countries, there is a shift from military to civil administration in the disaster management structures.</p>	NOVOTEC

Ethical, legal and societal aspects	Professional experience "Legal interoperability in case of cross border emergencies"	<p>Issue/gap: National laws and safeguards may constitute a limit to interoperability and data sharing if harmonization is not achieved</p> <p>Summary of the situation: Technical interoperability shall be addressed together with legal one in order to enable it by design</p>	SSSA
	Professional experience "underestimation of the "	<p>Type of emergency: ethical legal compliance is not addressed by design</p> <p>Issue/gap: breach in the data flows / sanctions by the competent authorities</p> <p>Summary of the situation: technical solutions might be vulnerable respect to external threats if compliance is not properly addressed. In addition the lack of ethical-legal compliance by design prohibits to enter into the market / expose the developers to sanctions / costs</p>	
Interoperability	Literature - "Patient transportation between countries"	<p>Doc name: Cross-border Health Care in the European Union. Mapping and analysing practices and policies</p> <p>Year: 2011</p> <p>Link: https://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0004/135994/e94875.pdf</p> <p>Justification: Emergency care is a field in which collaboration across borders can provide an obvious solution to the question of how to deploy rapid and potentially life-saving services. Due a to a national approach, "Patients are transported unnecessary distances in a failure to utilize more easily accessible cross-border provisions". Yet several cross-border projects have overcome this "centralism" by setting up arrangements which suit the local landscape; these can include reciprocal ambulance services, helicopter assistance...</p>	NOVOTEC
		<p>Doc name:</p> <p>Year:</p> <p>Link:</p> <p>Justification:</p>	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	<p>Type of emergency:</p> <p>Issue/gap:</p> <p>Summary of the situation:</p>	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	<p>Doc name:</p> <p>Year:</p> <p>Link:</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

WP4-Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Communication infrastructure	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies	Professional experience "Synchronization with other databases"	Type of emergency: Mobile Command and Control application it has its own database.	INDRA
		Issue/gap: The client expectations was to be fully integrated with external database from further services (Police, Firefighters, etc).	
		Summary of the situation: Allow permissions for third parties and provide data extraction mechanisms (integrations) by telematic gateway in web services or similar.	
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies	Professional experience "Cartographic updating "	Type of emergency: Mobile Command and Control application has to provide real-time GIS services.	INDRA
		Issue/gap: To avoid mobility risks for the most critical emergency services, the cartographic map shall be updated in real time. In previous projects it was critically mainly for the firefighters regarding specific evacuation areas or for the arrival at the catastrophe location.	
		Summary of the situation: In order to prevent delays and optimize the arrival times of emergency vehicles, the GIS system shall be updated on real time.	

The digitalisation on first aid actuations	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Other...Please add as many professional experience sections as you may need		Doc name:
Year:			
Link:			
Justification:			
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"		Doc name:
Year:			
Link:			
Justification:			

WP5- Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses

Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Knowledge exchange and access	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Maintenance, logistics and Deployment	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Command and Control and support to operational decision-making	Literature - 2 "Mobile Command and Control should provide an Standard Operation Procedures (SOP)"	Type of emergency: Mobile Command and Control should provide an Standard Operation Procedures (SOP).	IND
		Issue/gap: The operator from Mobile Command and Control may be helped by user guides for decision making in order to decide some actions or procedures for the catastrophe.	
		Summary of the situation: Regarding standaritzation procedures the application of Mobile Command and Control may be configurable in terms of incident.	
Common Operational Picture and warning	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	

WP6- Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing	Literature "Information sharing"	<p>Doc name: FOREST FIRES — Sparking firesmart policies in the EU FOREST FIRES — Sparking firesmart policies</p> <p>Link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/181116_booklet-forest-fire-hd.pdf</p> <p>Justification: "The uncertainty associated with the occurrence of extreme wildfire events requires integrated studies to understand the interaction among the main drivers of extreme fires. Information about wildfire dynamics and trends should be easily accessible to all bodies involved in the fire management process to improve understanding and decision-making capacities."</p>	NOVOTEC
	Literature "Centralized database"	<p>Doc name: FOREST FIRES — Sparking firesmart policies in the EU FOREST FIRES — Sparking firesmart policies in the EU. Year: 2018</p> <p>Link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/181116_booklet-forest-fire-hd.pdf</p> <p>Justification: "The uncertainty associated with the occurrence of extreme wildfire events requires integrated studies to understand the interaction among the main drivers of extreme fires. Information about wildfire dynamics and trends should be easily accessible to all bodies involved in the fire management process to improve understanding and decision-making capacities."</p>	NOVOTEC
Education and Training for first aid responses	Literature "Please add here the specific gap name"	<p>Doc name:</p> <p>Year:</p> <p>Link:</p>	
Raising practitioner and social awareness	Literature "Please add here the specific gap name"	<p>Doc name:</p> <p>Year:</p> <p>Link:</p> <p>Justification:</p>	
Civil-Military Cooperation	Literature "Please add here the specific gap name"	<p>Doc name:</p> <p>Year:</p> <p>Link:</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism	Professional experience "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Literature "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	

9. Annex C – Matrix UC1

VALKYRIES

Matrix UC1

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Other Contributors: TASSICA, SERMAS, HESE

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Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Ignacio Hernández	ignacio.hernandez@novotec.e	Novotec

Contributors

Name	Contact	Entity

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A/0	22/02/2022	All	Format adaptation
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PLANING

T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisisresponse planning. Leader(TASS)
T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:

Planing	Spain	Portugal
INSTITUTION		
TERRITORIAL EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLAN		
HAZARD-SPECIFIC EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLAN		
INTEGRATION PLAN		
HAZARD MAPPING		
RESOURCES MAPPING		
PERMANENT COMMAND AND CONTROL FACILITIES		
ACTIVATION RESPONSABILITY		
ACTIVATION CRITERIA		
ACTIVATION PROCEDURE		
CATEGORIZATION CRITERIA		
ALERT AND WARNING PLAN		
EVALUATION PLAN(emergency levels)		
LOCKDOWN PLAN		
SHELTER-IN-PLACE PLAN		
EVACUATION PLAN		
SHELTERING PLAN		
OPERATIONAL PLAN		
TACTICAL PLAN		
DEMOBILIZATION CRITERIA		
DEMOBILIZATION PROCEDURE		
PLAN DISSEMINATION		
PLAN IMPLEMENTARION		

PLAN TRAINING		
PLAN MAITENANCE		
PLAN REVIEW		

PLANING CHARTS
T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisisresponse planning. Leader(TASS)
T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)

Spanish charts

Contains: Risk maps/ Catalogue of available resources and location/ coordination procedures between the 2 countries

Portuguese charts

Figura II.1 – Estruturas de direção e coordenação política, estruturas de coordenação institucional e estruturas de comando operacional.

COMMAND & CONTROL T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making. Leader(ISEMI) Leader(TASS)		
TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		
Comand & Control	Spain	Portugal
INCIDENT COMMAND RESPONSABILITY		
INCIDENT COMMANDER	<p>1. Operation Coordination Centre function:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Declare the activation of the Plan and activate the response mechanisms and procedures of PLATERCAEX to each emergency situation. • Direct and coordinate emergency control actions within the territorial area of Extremadura. • Constitute, where appropriate, the CECOP/I. • Request extraordinary resources in the event of an emergency. • Identify with the support of the Steering Committee and the Technical Advisory Committee, the organizational structure that is activated in each of the situations, the operations, and at all times, the most appropriate actions emergency response and for the implementation of emergency the population, the environment, property and personnel attached to the Plan. • Notify other authorities of the occurrence of events likely to cause damage to people and goods. • To inform the population of the development of the emergency and of the self-protection to take through the Communication Centre, ensuring that the is accessible and intelligible to persons with disabilities. 	
LIAISON RESPONSABILITY		
COMMUNICATION RESPONSABILITY		

ALERT AND WARNING RESPONSABILITY		
SPECIAL TECHNICAL SUPPORT RESPONSABILITY		
SAFETY COMMAND		
OPERATIONS COMMAND		
LOGISTIC COMMAND		
MEDICAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE GLOBAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE FIREFIGHTERS COMMAND		
ON SCENE RESCUERS COMMAND		
ON SCENE SECURITY COMMAND		
ON SCENE FORENSIC COMMAND		
ON SCENE MEDICAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE LOGISTIC COMMAND		

FIRST RESPONDERS		
TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		
T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning. Leader(TASS)		
First Responders	Spain	Portugal
HAZARD CONTROL RESPONSABILITY		
DAMMAGE EVALUATION RESPONSABILITY		
ZONATION RESPONSABILITY		
ACCESS CONTROL RESPONSABILITY		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING RESPONSABILITY		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING COMMAND		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING PROCEDURE		
RESCUE RESPONSABILITY		
RESCUE TRIAGE COMMAND		
RESCUE TRIAGE PROCEDURE		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING RESPONSABILITY		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING COMMAND		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING PROCEDURE		
TREATMENT TRIAGE RESPONSABILITY		
TREATMENT TRIAGE COMMAND		
TREATMENT TRIAGE PROCEDURE		

STRETCHER TRANSPORT RESPONSABILITY		
STRETCHER TRANSPORT COMMAND		
STRETCHER TRANSPORT PROCEDURE		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE RESPONSABILITY		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE COMMAND		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE PROCEDURE		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE FACILITIES		
EVACUATION TRIAGE RESPONSABILITY		
EVACUATION TRIAGE COMMAND		
EVACUATION TRIAGE PROCEDURE		
EVACUATION RESPONSABILITY		
EVACUATION COMMAND		
EVACUATION PROCEDURE		

EMERGENCY LEVELS T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisisresponse planning. Leader (TASS) T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning. Leader (TASS) T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)		
TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		
Emergency levels	Spain	Portugal
INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL LOCAL LEVEL	Level 0: refers to those fires that can be controlled with the extinguishing means included in the INFOEX Plan and which, in their most likely evolution, do not pose a danger to civils, nor for goods other than those of natural forest nature, therefore it does not require express declaration or the deployment of any Civil Protection disposition.	
REGIONAL LEVEL	Level 1: Resources of Civil Protection are activated for those fires which can be controlled with the means and resources of extinction included in the INFOEX Plan, but it is foreseen, due to the fire’s possible evolution, a risk for civils and non-forest assets.	
NATIONAL LEVEL	Level 2: refers to fires in which, at the request of the INFOEX Coordination Plan, extraordinary state resources are needed or may involve situations of emergency situations where the national interest is at risk. This level may also be declared where the simultaneity of forest fires requires the incorporation of extraordinary means and resources.	
CROSS-NATIONAL LEVEL	Level 3: refers to those fires in which it has been considered that they are declared by the Ministry of the Interior. Forest fire fighting plan of the autonomous community of extremadura (INFOEX)	
INTERNATIONAL LEVEL		
MILITARY LEVEL		

MINIMUM EQUIPMENT (VEHICLES)
 T4.1 . First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units Leader(USN)
 T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	Spain	Portugal
Minimum equipment (Vehicles)		
FIREFIGHTERS VEHICLES		
FIREFIGHTERS PPE		
FIREFIGHTERS WEARABLES		
FIREFIGHTERS EVALUATION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS FORCES SIGNAGE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS HAZARD CONTROL EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS EXTINTION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS RESCUE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS ILUMINATION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS CBRNE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS COMM EQ		
SECURITY FORCES VEHICLES		
SECURITY FORCES PPE		
SECURITY FORCES WEARABLES		
SECURITY FORCES SIGNAGE EQ		
SECURITY FORCES COMM EQ		

	<p>Characteristics of vehicles (ambulances).</p> <p>1. All medical vehicles, in whatever class, shall comply with the following requirements, without prejudice to traffic, motor vehicle traffic, and road safety legislation:</p> <p>A) Identification and marking.</p> <p>a) External identification clearly distinguishing that it is an ambulance, through the inscription of the word «Ambulance» behind and in front. The front inscription will be made in reverse so that it can be read by reflection.</p> <p>b) Light and acoustic signaling, preferably by-pass, in accordance with the regulations in force.</p> <p>B) Mandatory documents.</p> <p>a) Record of disinfection of the carrier and equipment.</p> <p>b) Claims book.</p> <p>C) Vehicle.</p> <p>a) Vehicle with fiscal power, suspension, and brake systems following the transport of person regulation.</p> <p>b) Fog lamps (Front and rear).</p> <p>c) Intermittent stop indicators.</p> <p>d) Fire extinguisher, in accordance with the regulations.</p> <p>e) Winter tires, or alternatively ice and snow chains, at least for the period from November to March, inclusive.</p> <p>f) Tools for vehicle care.</p> <p>g) Triangular signals.</p> <p>D) Medical unit.</p> <p>a) Translucent windows (to ensure the privacy of the patient).</p> <p>b) Air conditioning and lighting independent of the driver's</p>	
EMS VEHICLES		
EMS PPE		
EMS WEARABLES		
EMS SIGNAGE EQ		
EMS TRIAGE EQ		
EMS MEDICAL CARE EQ		

EMS FACILITIES EQ		
EMS COMM EQ		

COMMUNICATION		
TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	T4.2 Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals. Leader (UMU) T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment. Leader (AREU) T4.3 The digitalization on first aid actuations. Leader (INDRA)	
Communication	Spain	Portugal
FIREFIGHTERS COMMUNICATIONS	<p>Firefighter Communications Equipment (extremadura): Radio station integrated into the communications network.</p> <p>Network established in each INFOEX Plan Coordination Zone, ground-to-ground (FM) communications are made using the following links or communication modalities:</p> <p>Simplex: When positioning the station on the channel, the frequency of transmission and reception is the same therefore, both the transmitters of the issuer and the receive the information, communicate directly with each other, without the need for any repeater.</p> <p>Semi-duplex: When we have to communicate with another station that is far away and there are intermediate obstacles we will use the channels we have for the semi-duplex mode.</p> <p>The frequencies of transmission and reception are different, so an intermediate element is needed to change the frequency of transmission in the reception, and the broadcasters can collect and interpret it. This element is the repeater, which is installed in a dominant point.</p> <p>In this mode, the sender throws the message, through his station, with the frequency of emission, it reaches the Repeater that instantaneously frequency of reception and the spear into the air, reaching the receiver, whose transmitter picks up the frequency and</p>	
RESCUERS COMMUNICATIONS		
SECURITY FORCES COMMUNICATIONS		
EMS COMMUNICATIONS		
MILITARY COMMUNICATIONS		
CIVIL PROTECTION COMMUNICATION		

RED CROSS COMMUNICATION		
OTHER INVOLVED RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS		
INTERINSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATIONS		
C&C COMMUNICATIONS		
CROSS-NATIONAL COMMUNICATIONS		

TRAINING T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses. Leader(BDI)		
TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		
Training	Spain	Portugal
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER FIREFIGHTERS		
FIREFIGHTERS MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE	Forest firefighters must: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pass an adequate selection process: knowledge of fire behavior and its extinction; in addition to passing physical tests that prove physical aptitude. - Receive continuous theoretical and practical training (new guidance, legislation, protocols) - Implement safety measures: wear Personal Protective Equipment, be aware of risk situations and the risk conditions to face them, take into account the OCEL protocol and apply the safety measures in the 	
FIREFIGHTERS ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING		
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER SECURITY FORCES		
SECURITY MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE		
SECURITY FORCES ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING		
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER EMS		

EMS MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE	<p>Minimum Training for Ambulances staff:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) Non-medical ambulances (classes A1 and A2) must have at least one driver holding at least the certificate of professionalism for medical transport provided for in Royal Decree 710/2011.b) Class B Medical Assistance Ambulances (basic life support) must have at least one driver who holds the professional training qualification of a medical emergency technician, as provided for in Royal Decree 1397/2007, or an approved or recognized foreign qualification and an assistant holding at least the same qualification.c) Class C Medical Assistance Ambulances (advanced life support) must have at least one driver possessing the above-mentioned professional training certificate of a medical emergency technician or a corresponding approved or recognized foreign qualification; with a nurse who holds a university degree in Nursing or a Bachelor's degree that qualifies for the exercise of the regulated profession of nursing, or a corresponding accredited or recognized foreign qualification. In addition, when assistance is required, a doctor must possess a university degree in Medicine or a Bachelor's degree that enables him to exercise the regulated profession of a doctor, or a corresponding foreign title approved or recognized.d) Voluntary staff performing the functions of driver or driver acting as assistant in ambulances intended for a humanitarian and social purpose of a general nature, must hold at least the certificate of professionalism of health transport provided for in Royal Decree 710/2011, of 20 May, two certificates of professionalism for the professional family Health which are included in the National Directory of Certificates of Professionalism, without being subject to the training requirements described in Article 4.1 of this Royal Decree.e) Spanish Red Cross and other charities referred to in the previous	
EMS ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING		

10. Annex D – Glossary

Acronym	Description
WP	Advanced Command Post
UC	Use Case
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
C&C	Command and Control
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
GA	Grant Agreement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GIS	Geographic Information System
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage

Table 1 - Glossary